

Project Title	Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC
Project Acronym	FAIR-IMPACT
Grant Agreement No.	101057344
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://fair-impact.eu/

M1.4 - Final public project meeting

Work Package	WP1, Project management, synchronisation & sustainability
Lead Author (Org)	Vasso Kalaitzi (KNAW-DANS)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Fanny Adloff (DKRZ), Joy Davidson (DCC), Ingrid Dillo (KNAW-DANS), Claudia D'Onofrio, (Trust-IT), Anne Sofie Fink (DeIC), Morane Gruenpeter (Software Heritage), Clement Jonquet (INRAE), Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, (Trust-IT), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Tommi Suominen (CSC), Mark van de Sanden (SURF), Maaïke Verburg (KNAW-DANS)
Due Date	2025-04-30
Date	2025-04-22
Version	V1.0
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15263697

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	09.04.2025	Vasso Kalaitzi (KNAW-DANS)	First draft of report
0.2	10.04.2025	Fanny Adloff (DKRZ), Joy Davidson (DCC), Ingrid Dillo (KNAW-DANS), Claudia D’Onofrio, (Trust-IT), Anne Sofie Fink (DeIC), Morane Gruenpeter (Software Heritage), Clement Jonquet (INRAE), Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, (Trust-IT), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Tommi Suominen (CSC), Mark van de Sanden (SURF), Maaike Verburg (KNAW-DANS)	Integration of individual session summary reports
1.0	22.04.2025	Vasso Kalaitzi (KNAW-DANS), Layan Nijem (KNAW-DANS), Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Addressing open comments and finalising.

Disclaimer

FAIR-IMPACT has received funding from the European Commission’s Horizon Europe funding programme for research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101057344. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Description of the Milestone	5
2.1 Role of the milestone	5
2.1.1 Means of verification	6
3. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC	6
4. Conclusions and next steps	7
5. Appendices	8
5.1 Welcome and Introduction	8
5.2 Adopters' Marketplace Elevator Pitches	8
5.2.1 Minute madness, Marketplace area and programme	8
5.3 F for Findability: Persistent Identifiers and Knowledge Graph	8
5.3.1 Session objectives	8
5.3.2 Main points from the session	9
5.3.3 Conclusions/Next steps	9
5.4 A for Accessibility: Semantic Artefacts	10
5.4.1 Session objectives	10
5.4.2 Main points from the session	10
5.4.3 Conclusions/Next steps	11
5.5 Supporting FAIR Implementation: FAIR-IMPACT stories & FAIRCORE4EOSC Case Studies	11
5.5.1 Session objectives	11
5.5.2 Main points from the session	11
5.5.3 Conclusions/Next steps	12
5.6 I for Interoperability: from technical to legal interoperability	12
5.6.1 Session objectives	12
5.6.2 Main points from the session	12
5.6.3 Conclusions/Next steps	12
5.7 R for reusability: Certifications, metrics and guidelines for FAIR data and Software	12
5.7.1 Session objectives	12
5.7.2 Main points from the session	13
5.7.3 Conclusions/Next steps	13
5.8 Concluding session: Reflections from Stakeholders	14
5.8.1 Session objectives	14
5.8.2 Conclusions	14

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
HPC	High-Performance Computing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PHIDIAS	Prototype of HPC/Data Infrastructure for On-demand Services
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
PID	Persistent Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
PIDMR	PID Meta Resolver
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
RDGraph	Research Discovery Graph
HLAC	High level Advisory Board

1. Introduction

The FAIR-IMPACT project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission, under Horizon Europe. During its lifetime of three years, the FAIR-IMPACT project has actively supported the implementation of FAIR-enabling practices, tools and services, across geographies and scientific communities at European, national and institutional levels.

FAIR-IMPACT placed its focus on Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), Metadata and ontologies, Metrics and Interoperability. Engagement with a wide range of stakeholders has been achieved through Synchronisation efforts with relevant projects and initiatives in the EOSC and FAIR ecosystems, extensive communication activities and events, and an elaborate support programme including financial support, expert (non-financial) support and public FAIR Implementation workshops.

During its implementation, FAIR-IMPACT established and maintained collaboration with several other INFRAEOSC projects,¹ and more especially with the FAIRCORE4EOSC² project. FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC worked closely and decided to organise jointly their key events, such as the Kick-off meeting, shared annual sessions, and their closing event, the FAIRfest.³

The present document represents a brief summary report of the FAIRfest, by also referring to the glossy version⁴ that is available for the general public.

2. Description of the Milestone

The present milestone is a brief summary report of the FAIRfest, the final public meeting of FAIR-IMPACT, which was organised in collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project in the Hague, the Netherlands on February 20th and 21st 2025. Individual summary reports per session are available in the Appendices.

2.1 Role of the milestone

The role of this milestone is to provide a concise report on the FAIR-IMPACT final project meeting, i.e. the FAIRfest, hoping to inform the readers on the event content, and offer pointers to the event's materials.

¹ Projects funded under Horizon Europe's chapter for Research Infrastructures and directly contributing to the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

² <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fairfest-celebrating-advancements-fair-solutions-eosc>

⁴ Adloff, F., Davidson, J., Fink, A. S., Gruenpeter, M., Jonquet, C., Kalaitzi, V., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Nordling, J., Suominen, T., van de Sanden, M., Verburg, M., & D'Onofrio, C. (2025). FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC_post event report. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC, The Hague, The Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15234134>

2.1.1 Means of verification

As the FAIRfest was jointly organised by FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC but its value and interest goes beyond the two projects, the two communications teams chose to create a specific FAIRfest Zenodo community⁵ to include all relevant materials. The information is also accessible through the project's website,⁶ including the programme and proceedings, the picture gallery, and the post-event (glossy version) report⁷ available for the general public. The means of verification are the present report and Appendices, as well as the event's materials, that are publicly available on the FAIR-IMPACT website and the FAIRfest community on Zenodo.

3. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC

To close a successful cycle of implementation and collaboration, the two projects were looking for opportunities to co-locate their final public events into one wider event, which would have the character of celebrating achievements towards FAIR-enabling solutions in the context of the EOSC and beyond. At the same time, FAIR-IMPACT wanted to seize the opportunity to showcase progress to its target communities and invite them to provide input and validation before the submission of its final outputs.

The FAIRfest took place on February 20th and 21st 2025 in the Hague, the Netherlands next to the 19th edition of the International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC25).⁸ Co-locating the event in Madurodam⁹ next to a Conference very relevant for the two projects' target stakeholders provided the opportunity for an interesting, international audience on-site while minimising travelling needs: researchers and data practitioners, data stewards, data service providers and repository managers, research performing organisation staff, open science national level initiatives, and representatives of projects, initiatives, and actors in both EOSC and FAIR ecosystems took part in this celebration. At the same time, to provide an inclusive opportunity for engagement and participation, the FAIRfest was organised as a hybrid event.

The FAIRfest was planned as a festival celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in the European Open Science research landscape around four pillars:

- F for Findability: Persistent identifiers & Knowledge Graphs

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/fairfest25/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fairfest-celebrating-advancements-fair-solutions-eosc>

⁷ Adloff, F., Davidson, J., Fink, A. S., Gruenpeter, M., Jonquet, C., Kalaitzi, V., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Nordling, J., Suominen, T., van de Sanden, M., Verburg, M., & D'Onofrio, C. (2025). FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC_post event report. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC, The Hague, The Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15234134>

⁸ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc>

⁹ <https://www.madurodam.nl/en>

- A for Accessibility: Semantic Artefacts
- I for Interoperability: from the technical to legal interoperability
- R for Reusability: Certification, metrics & guidelines for FAIR data and software.

Next to plenary sessions, keynotes and parallel discussions, case studies and use cases took the spotlight and triggered the discussion among members of the community. FAIR-enabling solutions adopters and implementers participated in a showcase area that consisted of the FAIRfest Marketplace. The crowd had the chance to listen to pitches, visit the different stands and poster areas, discuss challenges, solutions and best practices and ask questions. FAIRCORE4EOSC technical components were explained further, while participants listened to FAIR implementation stories based on the outcomes of the successful FAIR-IMPACT support programme. Members of the FAIR-IMPACT High Level Advisory Committee, FAIR Champions and ambassadors, interoperability experts and practitioners, supported organisation and individuals, as well as representatives of other relevant projects and initiatives were given the opportunity to have exchange knowledge and views on future steps in relation to the the implementation of the FAIR principles.

Next to the full programme,¹⁰ picture gallery,¹¹ official FAIRfest video¹² and FAIRfest Zenodo community, summaries from individual sessions are available below as Appendices.

4. Conclusions and next steps

The FAIRfest provided an opportunity to the FAIR and EOSC community to celebrate the advancements that derived from the implementation of the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects. This celebration started with the hope that the projects' achievements and outputs will be used as the stepping stones for further development towards FAIR implementation in the context of the EOSC, and closed with identified challenges, thoughts and aspirations, not only for the future of research through a FAIR environment of solutions, practices, services and policies, but for the future of the EOSC as well.

Highlights and conclusions per session are available in the Appendices and the published (glossy version) of the post-event report.

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/fairfest-programme>

¹¹ <https://www.flickr.com/photos/202331412@N03/albums/72177720324101355/>

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RcO6Z-rgPXA&t=2s>

5. Appendices

5.1 Welcome and Introduction

The FAIRfest is the closing event of two projects funded by the European Commission: FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC: each in their own way these projects were focused on the implementation of FAIR for the EOSC. As twin projects with complimentary goals the projects kicked off in a combined event almost three years ago and the circle is closed with a combined event to celebrate the advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC.

In their opening remarks the two project coordinators welcomed the participants in the room as well as online. They provided a high level overview of the current state of implementation of the FAIR principles in the European data landscape and introduced the FAIRfest programme.

The programme aimed to celebrate the advancements we have made as a community, because we have certainly come a long way. At the FAIRfest, the projects took stock of where we are now, looked to the future and discussed the challenges ahead; challenges that will be picked up again by new initiatives and European projects in the years to come. The two coordinators expressed their hope that the results from both projects, will be used to build upon for further developments.

5.2 Adopters' Marketplace Elevator Pitches

5.2.1 Minute madness, Marketplace area and programme

During the FAIRfest 14 adopters and implementers of FAIR enabling solutions, tools, methodologies and practices were invited to provide a showcase in the Marketplace area on a stage during coffee and lunch breaks. During this session the audience had the opportunity to witness a minute madness¹³ as introduction of the adopters' presence at the FAIRfest. The Marketplace and poster area¹⁴ were arranged in such a way that the audience could navigate, ask questions and discuss with the presenters and other participants.

5.3 F for Findability: Persistent Identifiers and Knowledge Graph

5.3.1 Session objectives

The session F for Findability discussed the crucial role of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and supporting tools and services in enhancing findability and discoverability of research outcomes and the importance of good practices and policy conformance when using PIDs. In an EOSC context, PIDs constitute vital building blocks when forming the EOSC Federation. However, PIDs and their impact on research findability is based on a multifaceted framework, which requires establishment of sustainable collaboration frameworks and

¹³ <https://fair-impact.eu/adopters-marketplace-programme>

¹⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/fairfest-marketplace-area>

convergence through the involvement of various stakeholders to ensure robustness and consistency.

5.3.2 Main points from the session

We are observing emerging trends in EOSC related to PIDs, such as introductions of basic features for authorisation and the protection of sensitive data at the PID level. Other trends include typing in PIDs through the FDO Forum and the Research Data Alliance, and emerging PID types. It is good to keep an eye out on these developments.

New PID services and tools, such as the PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR), the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) developed in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, and Research Activity Identifier developed in collaboration with ARDC, were presented. PIDMR integrates different systems, is able to route different PID types, and improves machine-actionability. The service also facilitates the standardised use of PIDs to promote effective data management and data analytics while supporting FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). CAT encodes, records, and queries compliance with the EOSC policy and is scalable to also encompass compliance assessments with other frameworks. RAiD functions as a PID, a registry, and a collaborative metadata management system, thus serving multiple purposes. The service provides persistent, unique and resolvable information linking organisations, project members, inputs and outputs, enabling long term impact analysis.

Scientific knowledge graphs (SKGs) are vital for enhancing discoverability of research outputs. Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) and PIDGraph comprise cross-disciplinary (metadata) maps of science used for discovery and research assessment. It was emphasised that although PIDs in SKGs enhance findability, misuse and non-compliance with policies can create potential authoritativeness, reliability, and consistency issues. Clear usage policies and robust quality control measures are essential to ensure proper implementation and adherence.

Practical guidelines on PID implementation and usage help navigate the concerned stakeholder in complying to best practices and in accordance with the EOSC. FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC have in collaboration produced supporting documents, such as:

- PID guides for national level initiatives, service providers and institutions, which is a hands-on framework for adopting PIDs in alignment with EOSC policies and core solutions providing clear, actionable steps for incorporating PIDs into existing workflows
- Guidelines for PID Managers to support them in formulating and assessing PID policies in a standard, comprehensive, user-friendly and EOSC compliant manner
- End user guidelines on best practices of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for end users, as defined by seven integrated use case partners participating in the FAIR-IMPACT project.

5.3.3 Conclusions/Next steps

Updating the EOSC PID Policy is fundamental for the EOSC Federation. The EOSC Nodes should have their own PID policies in place and can easily assess their compliance with the EOSC PID Policy through the Compliance Assessment Toolkit and get useful information on PID implementation through the related Knowledge Base (in which published practical guides will be included). All relevant stakeholders within EOSC need to get engaged in the multi-layered PID landscape to achieve convergence and take joint actions in furthering the utilisation of PIDs when necessary. A growing number of valuable guidelines, services, and tools are now available to support various stakeholders in advancing PID implementation, usage, and policy—so let's put them to use!

5.4 A for Accessibility: Semantic Artefacts

5.4.1 Session objectives

This joint plenary session aimed to highlight the transformative contributions of the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects in advancing FAIR principles in the domain of semantics, focusing on metadata & ontologies, mappings, and research software. The session provided an opportunity to reflect on achievements, evaluate impact, and collaboratively envision the future of FAIR-compliant and semantically enabled science within EOSC.

5.4.2 Main points from the session

The session opened with a keynote by Carole Goble (University of Manchester), emphasising that accessibility is a critical aspect of FAIR. She argued that without access, data and software effectively do not exist, highlighting the risks posed by missing object archives. Carole stressed that access is not just about protocols—semantics matter and require robust infrastructure, capacity-building, and equitable participation. She also addressed controlled and inclusive access, ensuring that semantic artefact infrastructure and services remain available to all researchers, including those in underrepresented communities. AI's growing role in metadata automation and semantic accessibility was also discussed, with an emphasis on maintaining transparency and usability in AI-driven solutions.

This keynote set the stage for a series of presentations showcasing key advancements from both projects:

- **Research Software Metadata Guidelines:** Developed within FAIR-IMPACT, including contributions to the CodeMeta vocabulary and the Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) from FAIRCORE4EOSC.
- **FAIR Mappings Recommendations & MSCR Service:** Outlined best practices for making mappings FAIR and introduced the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) as a key component for interoperability.
- **FAIR Semantic Artefacts and their Catalogues:** Showcased the development and consolidation of semantic artefact catalogues, with multidisciplinary efforts toward federation and interoperability models to ensure sustainability.

- DTR on the Roadmap for FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs): Demonstrated how the Data Type Registry (DTR) contributes to the implementation of FAIR Digital Objects, improving machine-actionability and data interoperability.

The session concluded with a panel discussion centered on aligning project outcomes with EOSC objectives, long-term sustainability of semantic artefacts, and the challenges of funding, governance, and integration within the broader research ecosystem. An important topic, mappings and crosswalks (previously presented), came back several times in the discussion showing the need for convergence and continued effort on this particular topic in the EOSC context.

5.4.3 Conclusions/Next steps

Ensuring the long-term accessibility of semantic artefacts requires sustainable production services and reliable governance, yet funding challenges persist. Over the past few years, the design and adoption of FAIR semantics artefacts has grown –including thanks to the contribution of FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC– but implementation hurdles remain. The next steps involve strengthening semantic interoperability, shared governance, continuous support of semantic artefact related services , and ensuring that FAIR semantic artefacts remain accessible and usable across diverse research communities. Further collaboration is needed to integrate semantic artefacts services (such as the presented OntoPortal or MSCR tools) into the EOSC distributed ecosystem, improve FAIR mappings and semantic artefacts catalogues, and explore AI-driven approaches to enhance automation and usability.

5.5 Supporting FAIR Implementation: FAIR-IMPACT stories & FAIRCORE4EOSC Case Studies

5.5.1 Session objectives

This session aimed to share the experiences of those who participated in one of the sixteen support actions and programmes offered by the FAIR-IMPACT¹⁵ project. Following a very brief recap of the support routes provided by FAIR-IMPACT, the session then moved on to hear from six panelists who joined one or more of our support actions and/or programmes, and the participation of 16 online and 35 onsite individuals.

5.5.2 Main points from the session

Each of the panelists shared a brief summary of the FAIR-IMPACT support action/programme they participated in and provided an update on what they have done to progress the FAIR-enabling capacity of their organisation or service. Overall, the panellists shared that they had very positive experiences during their engagement with FAIR-IMPACT support and it was truly inspiring to hear that all of the panellists are continuing to put what they learned into practice in various ways. The opportunity to exchange knowledge with peers during the support actions and programmes was something that the panelists particularly valued. According to one of the panelists (Beth Knazook, Digital Repository of Ireland): “You get

¹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-open-calls-support>

better by participating in communities. You don't get better on your own". We couldn't agree more!

5.5.3 Conclusions/Next steps

The individual experiences and ongoing work of each of the panelists constitute the conclusion and insight into next steps from this session.

5.6 I for Interoperability: from technical to legal interoperability

5.6.1 Session objectives

Solving the I of FAIR is probably one of the biggest challenges in adopting and implementing FAIR practices. While many research communities have existing practices to manage interoperability within their domain. The significant challenges start when research data and other artifacts need to be shared across domains. And this sharing across domains will only increase because most of the societal challenges (e.g. climate change, health, environment, energy transition and artificial intelligence) require cross-domain solutions. Interoperability is not only a technical challenge but more frequently a challenge on the semantic, organisational, and legal level. The EOSC Interoperability Framework from 2021 addresses these challenges at the conceptual level. For the implementation level additional effort in the form of recommendations, guidelines, best practices, prototyping etc. This session focused on how to bridge between the legal, organisational, semantic, and technical (LOST) interoperability stack and explore future ways to support an interdisciplinary approach for a FAIR EOSC.

5.6.2 Main points from the session

The session investigated how to bridge between the legal, organisational, semantic, and technical (LOST) interoperability stack and explore future ways to support an interdisciplinary approach for a FAIR EOSC.

5.6.3 Conclusions/Next steps

Interoperability in terms of legal, organisation, semantic and technical aspects is and remains a challenge, especially when research data and artifacts need to be shared across domains. This cross-disciplinary exchange only increases this challenge in difficulty. Although the EOSC Interoperability Framework (2021)¹⁶ does address these challenges at conceptual level, more cross-discipline interaction, collaboration and solutions are needed, while also taking stock from the recommendations, guidelines, best practices and prototyping from the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects.

5.7 R for reusability: Certifications, metrics and guidelines for FAIR data and Software

5.7.1 Session objectives

¹⁶ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1>

In the session R for Reusability, the participants had the opportunity to discuss the question: Are the FAIR principles enough for reusability? The session followed an interactive format that allowed the participants to ask the hard hitting questions on Reusability to a panel of experts. The audience had the opportunity to reflect on their own services and solutions (e.g. Research Software API and Connector from Zenodo to SWH, F-UJI,¹⁷ Compliance Assessment Toolkit,¹⁸ the Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR¹⁹ and more) and consider what they contribute to Reusability, opening up to critical questions, suggestions, and use cases.

5.7.2 Main points from the session

The session started by the audience getting to know each other and their experiences and perspectives when considering FAIR and Reusability. This facilitated an all-round lively and interactive session. Next, the panel members introduced themselves and their solutions towards reusability; these included the Compliance Assessment Toolkit, the prototype for transparent repository information exposure, the Zenodo InvenioRDM APIs connection to Software Heritage, the FAIR assessment metrics for software, and semantic artefact reusability. After these introductions of some FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT efforts towards improved reusability, the audience again discussed with each other some critical questions, each leading to some concluding panel reflections. Do we care about Reusability? What is the scope of Reusability? The audience was invited to ask the questions they had always had on their mind but never dared to ask.

5.7.3 Conclusions/Next steps

The session ended with considering the future of the topic after the end of FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT: what's next? Each panel member presented their final thoughts on the topic. These statements are as follows:

Herve L'Hours (UESSEX/UKDS): "Reusability is an incredible target to hit, you need to define what you are working towards, how, and when you'll know you've reached it."

Elena Breitmoser (UEDIN-SSI): There is a need for FAIR and beyond for your object. But how do we make sure we don't diverge too much in the disciplines once FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT end? How do we build a community for sharing input and preventing reinvented wheels?

Daniel Garijo (UPM): There is a clear importance of the documentation of a resource when looking into the future. Usage examples are essential, even though they're out of the direct scope of FAIR. For better reusability, ask if others would be able to reuse your own resource as it is.

Alex Ioannidis (CERN): As a service provider, think about user experience. How do we work in the background to capture the needed information without burdening researchers? But also, educating researchers is still important at the same time.

¹⁷ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-assessment-tools>

¹⁸ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

¹⁹ <https://w3id.org/foops>

Wim Hugo (KNAW DANS): Certified repositories are only the tip of the iceberg. There are about 150 certified repositories worldwide currently, but there are about 3000 existing repositories captured in re3data and even more repositories that likely exist outside of that. The challenge ahead is quite enormous to get these good practices across a much larger order of magnitude.

5.8 Concluding session: Reflections from Stakeholders

5.8.1 Session objectives

In the closing panel session representatives of the stakeholder communities addressed by the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects had the opportunity to look back on over a decade of FAIR implementation: 11 years since the FAIR Data Principles workshop in Lorentz, 9 years since the publication in Scientific Data and 7 years since the Turning FAIR into Reality report,²⁰ and address the following questions: Where are we now? Where did the audience expect these communities to be? What has changed and what is the same? Are we working on the right things? What is needed in the future to Turn FAIR into Reality?

5.8.2 Conclusions

In this session under the chairing and moderation of Carole Goble (UNIMAN), the panelists shared their views on the implementation of FAIR principles and FAIR enabling solutions in the European Open Science landscape.

Natalie Harrower (Canadian Research Data Centre Network and FAIR-IMPACT HLAC member) focused on how we retain FAIR within this changing world context, also looking at security concerns. She insisted that we need to treat our data as a national asset. Today the mantra is “protecting” our data from foreign influence, DURC - Do use research of concerns. Efficiency is also very much needed. From an international perspective, the coordination of thinking and organising this and EOSC is providing some organising goal. In Canada this motivating big picture is probably not available yet.

Andrew Treloar (Australian Research Data Commons) started with a provocative question: Do researchers need to know about FAIR? How much do you know about how electricity works in your house? We should make things easIER and slow down the complexity. While a huge amount of work is on show, some of the cases will not become reality. Furthermore, the generality of solutions often comes at a cost. With an eye on sustainability, which is a great challenge, we and the projects need to learn from the infrastructure that has sustained solutions over time.

Karel Luijben (European Open Science Cloud Association) reflected on the fact that we are well on the way and enormous progress has been made since the Lorentz conference. If in 2040 50% of research output would be as FAIR as possible it would be a very good outcome. Resistance to open science is often linked to culture, lack of training and concerns within our organisations. Perseverance, patience and power to push are needed to get further. With regards to projects, he identified two different types: those with implementable resources

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.2777/54599>

and those that are exploring new territories. He also urged the audience to look into the future.

Pantelis Tziveloglou (European Commission, DG Research and Innovation) EOSC can have a very significant role in contributing to competitiveness and in addressing security aspects, by also contributing to a European Knowledge commons. AI is coming up very relevant on the market and AI factories were at the moment of the event being launched. EOSC should be something that every single researcher in Europe should know about, even if not dealing with it in their daily life, and we are not there yet.